

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ADVECTION AND FILAMENTATION OF A PASSIVE SCALAR ON TOROIDAL STREAM SURFACES

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Abstract

We investigate the three-dimensional advection and filamentation of a localized passive scalar on toroidal stream surfaces, motivated by the internal structure of the Hill vortex [4, 8]. Using a geometrically consistent model [10] in which particle motion is constrained to invariant tori and governed by differential angular velocities, we construct a Lagrangian description of scalar transport on a torus. The scalar field $\chi(s, \theta, t)$ evolves according to the advection equation $D\chi/Dt = 0$, with trajectories defined by coupled toroidal and poloidal motions. Starting from an initially localized Gaussian patch, we show that differential rotation along the torus leads to progressive stretching and folding, resulting in the formation of thin filamentary structures. Through a combination of three-dimensional surface visualization, meridional cross-sections, and unwrapped toroidal coordinates, we demonstrate that the scalar distribution undergoes systematic deformation characterized by longitudinal elongation and transverse compression. This leads to a rapid amplification of scalar gradients, with $\max|\nabla\chi|$ exhibiting near-exponential growth, while the transverse filament thickness decreases algebraically in time. The unwrapped representation reveals the underlying shear mechanism as a linear growth of phase differences, producing quasi-periodic layered structures. These results provide a clear geometric and dynamical interpretation of scalar mixing on invariant tori, highlighting the role of differential advection in generating fine-scale structures even in steady, integrable flows. The proposed framework links three-dimensional vortex dynamics with toroidal transport and offers insight into the early stages of mixing, as well as the precursors to nonlinear and dissipative effects in vortex-dominated flows.

Keywords: passive scalar transport; advection; filamentation; invariant tori; Hill vortex; toroidal coordinates; Lagrangian dynamics; differential rotation; shear flow; scalar mixing; vortex dynamics; meridional cross-section; gradient amplification; vortex-induced transport; coherent structures

1. Introduction. The problem of passive scalar transport in incompressible flows with closed streamlines has been studied extensively. Classical works in this area are associated with the analysis of differential advection and mixing in integrable flows [13-18]. In particular, the studies of P. B. Rhines and W. R. Young [16] demonstrated that even in fully regular flows with closed trajectories, effective "mixing" can occur due to the stretching and winding of a passive scalar. These works showed that the dependence of angular velocity on the invariant of motion leads to a linear growth of phase differences and, consequently, to filamentation.

These ideas were later developed in the context of geophysical flows and nonlinear dynamics, for example in the works of N. J. Balmforth [5, 6], where processes of stretching and the formation of thin layers in jet-like and vortical structures were investigated. However, these studies typically considered either two-dimensional models or passive scalar transport without explicit account of three-dimensional geometries such as toroidal surfaces.

From a geometric and dynamical perspective, the present formulation is directly related to the theory of invariant tori in Hamiltonian systems. The works of Vladimir Arnold and Jürgen Moser [3, 12] showed that in integrable systems the motion takes place on invariant tori parameterized by angular variables. In such systems, the dynamics can be written in the form

$$\dot{s} = \omega_s(I), \theta = \omega_\theta(I), \quad (1)$$

where I is the action variable (an analogue of ψ). The dependence of the frequencies on I gives rise to phase shifts and leads to the *winding* of trajectories. However, in the classical KAM theory [3], neither the distribution of a passive scalar nor its filamentation was considered. In this work, we therefore provide a physical interpretation that complements the classical Hamiltonian framework [9], extending it to the advection and deformation of a localized scalar field.

On the other hand, there exists an extensive body of literature in fluid dynamics devoted to vortex structures and their internal dynamics. The works of H. K. Moffatt [11] and S. Childress & A.D. Gilbert [7] investigated the stretching and deformation of vortex lines, as well as the topology of flow fields. However, the primary focus of these studies was on vortex dynamics itself, rather than on the transport of a passive scalar on invariant surfaces.

Finally, there is a well-established line of research known as chaotic advection [1-2], which demonstrates that even simple steady or time-periodic flows can generate highly complex scalar structures. The key distinction in the present case, however, is that the flow under consideration is integrable rather than chaotic. Despite this, it still produces complex scalar distributions due to the presence of shear. Thus, the complexity observed here arises not from chaotic trajectories, but from differential advection in a regular flow.

2. Advection. It should be noted that the problem of passive scalar transport in incompressible flows with closed streamlines is closely related to the fundamental concept of chaotic advection introduced by Hassan Aref. In his seminal work [1], Aref (1984) demonstrated that even simple laminar flows can generate highly complex scalar distributions through the mechanism of stretching and folding, described by the advection equation

$$D\chi/Dt = (\partial\chi/\partial t) + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla\chi. \quad (2)$$

In such systems, the complexity of the scalar structure is determined not by turbulence, but by the kinematics of trajectories and the properties of the flow as a dynamical system. In contrast to classical examples of chaotic advection, where the dynamics of Lagrangian trajectories is non-integrable and characterized by positive Lyapunov exponents, the motion in the present case remains regular and takes place on invariant toroidal surfaces. The particle trajectories are described by the system

$$ds/st = \omega_s(\theta), d\theta/dt = \omega_\theta, \quad (3)$$

where both frequencies are smooth functions, and the phase space contains no chaotic regions. Nevertheless, as emphasized in subsequent studies on Lagrangian kinematics, the key mechanism responsible for the formation of complex structures is not chaos per se, but rather the presence of shear, which leads to the linear growth of phase differences.

$$\Delta s(t) \sim \omega'_s(\theta)t. \quad (4)$$

Thus, the filamentation of the passive scalar shown in the figure can be viewed as a particular case of the more general framework proposed by Aref, in which stretching and winding act as universal mechanisms for the generation of fine-scale structure. However, in contrast to classical chaotic advection, where stretching is exponential and associated with chaotic trajectories, $|\delta\chi(t)| \sim e^{\lambda t}$, the flow in the present case remains integrable, and the increasing complexity of the scalar field is governed by differential advection on invariant tori. This leads to a quasi-linear growth of phase differences and an algebraic decrease of transverse scales,

$$\ell_\perp(t) \sim 1/(1 + \Omega't), \quad (5)$$

accompanied by a simultaneous amplification of scalar gradients.

Thus, the obtained results extend the classical theory of Aref by demonstrating that the formation of thin filaments and effective “mixing” of a passive scalar can occur even in fully regular three-dimensional flows without chaos. In this sense, the dynamics considered here occupies an intermediate position between integrable systems and regimes of chaotic advection, combining the geometric regularity of trajectories with the kinematic complexity of the scalar distribution.

3. Problem formulation and governing equations. The underlying idea is that in an axisymmetric flow with closed streamlines, each level set $\psi = \text{const}$ in the meridional plane, when rotated about the axis of symmetry, generates a toroidal surface. If the motion of a particle along such a surface is then prescribed with two angular components - poloidal and toroidal - a localized patch of passive scalar is advected along trajectories, gradually stretching into a long, thin filament.

Accordingly, the visualization is constructed as a schematic computational model of passive scalar transport on a toroidal surface. It does not represent a direct numerical solution of the full three-dimensional Euler equations for the Hill vortex, but rather a geometrically and kinematically consistent approximation. This approach allows one to clearly illustrate the processes of stretching, winding, and filamentation of a localized scalar patch on a family of toroidal stream surfaces.

The computational visualization is based on a Lagrangian simulation of passive scalar transport on an invariant toroidal surface, which approximates a family of streamlines in an axisymmetric flow. The construction begins with the specification of the torus geometry. In the standard parametrization, a torus with major radius R and minor (tube) radius a is described using two angular coordinates: the toroidal angle s and the poloidal angle θ . In Cartesian coordinates, this parametrization is given by

$$x = (R + a \cos \theta) \cos s, y = (R + a \cos \theta) \sin s, z = a \sin \theta, \quad (6)$$

where R is the major radius of the torus and a is the radius of the tube. All transport computations are carried out in the parametric coordinates (s, θ) , which allows for the use of periodic boundary conditions and avoids complications associated with surface curvature. The numerical data are constructed in this parametric representation using the angular variables (s, θ) , где $s \in [0, 2\pi)$, the toroidal angle, and $\theta \in [-\pi, \pi)$ the poloidal angle. The geometry of the surface is defined through the standard mapping into three-dimensional space given by equations (6). Such a surface serves as a three-dimensional analogue of a single invariant torus in the Hill vortex: in the physical problem, its shape is determined by the streamfunction, whereas in the present visualization it is replaced by an idealized circular torus in order to clearly illustrate the transport mechanism.

Next, a passive scalar field $\chi = \chi(s, \theta, t)$ is defined on this surface, which satisfies the pure advection equation:

$$D\chi/Dt = (\partial\chi/\partial t) + \dot{s}(\partial\chi/\partial s) + \dot{\theta}(\partial\chi/\partial\theta) = 0. \quad (7)$$

This implies that the scalar concentration is conserved along Lagrangian trajectories. Therefore, the problem reduces to prescribing the kinematics on the torus, i.e., specifying the evolution laws for \dot{s} and $\dot{\theta}$. For the purposes of visualization, a simple model was adopted with constant poloidal velocity and differential toroidal velocity:

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega_\theta, \dot{s} = \omega_s(\theta), \quad (8)$$

where $\omega_\theta = \text{const}$, and $\omega_s(\theta)$ is a smooth periodic function that generates differential advection. To reproduce winding and shear, the toroidal velocity was taken to depend on the position on the torus, for example in the form

$$\omega_s(\theta) = \omega_0 + \varepsilon \cos \theta, \quad (9)$$

or in an equivalent form with smooth periodic modulation. The parameters ω_0 and ε were chosen so as to ensure a noticeable phase shift while preserving the regular (non-chaotic) structure of the trajectories.

The resulting velocity field is divergence-free on the toroidal surface and preserves measure, which corresponds to the condition

$$\nabla_s \cdot \mathbf{u}_\tau = 0, \tag{10}$$

where \mathbf{u}_τ denotes the divergence-free tangential velocity field on the toroidal surface.

It is precisely this dependence of ω_s on θ in equation (9) that generates **differential advection**: different parts of the scalar patch, located at slightly different poloidal positions, move along the torus with different velocities. As a result, the phase shift between two nearby particles grows in time as

$$\Delta s(t) \approx \omega'_s(\theta) \Delta \theta t, \tag{11}$$

and the patch is stretched into a long filament.

At the initial moment, the scalar field is prescribed as a localized Gaussian patch on the torus:

$$\chi(s, \theta, 0) = \exp(-((s - s_0)/m_s)^2 - ((\theta - \theta_0)/m_\theta)^2), \tag{12}$$

where $m_s = \sqrt{2}\sigma_s$ and $m_\theta = \sqrt{2}\sigma_\theta$.

Since the angular variables are periodic, the numerical implementation accounts for periodic continu-

ation in both s and θ , meaning that distances are measured along the shortest arc on the circle. The solution at any time is then expressed in Lagrangian form as:

$$\chi(s, \theta, t) = \chi_0(S_{-t}(s, \theta), \Theta_{-t}(s, \theta)), \tag{13}$$

where (S_t, Θ_t) denotes the flow map generated by the dynamical system

$$ds/dt = \omega_s(\theta), d\theta/dt = \omega_\theta. \tag{14}$$

In other words, to obtain the scalar concentration at a point (s, θ) at time t , one must trace this point backward along its trajectory and evaluate the initial field at the corresponding location. In a discrete visualization, this can be achieved either by integrating an ensemble of particles or by directly advecting a grid-based field. In the present implementation, a Lagrangian approach was employed: a set of tracer points carrying scalar values χ_i was constructed, these particles were then advected along trajectories, and subsequently a smoothed scalar field on the toroidal surface was reconstructed from their distribution.

Figure 1. Evolution of scalar concentration $\chi(x, t)$ along closed helical trajectories on a torus

4. Visualization of scalar advection and results.

To obtain the first row of figures (Fig. 1) from the described dynamics, the torus was visualized as a three-dimensional surface colored according to the scalar field $\chi(x, y, z, t)$. For this purpose, each point on the surface with parameters (s, θ) was mapped into Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) using the parametrization given above, and the value $\chi(s, \theta, t)$ was used to define

the color. As a result, the first row clearly illustrates the evolution of the scalar patch: an initially compact region progressively elongates along trajectories and wraps around the torus. At early times, the structure appears as a single stretched patch; subsequently, it develops into a long, thin filament, and at later times it forms a system of multiple narrow, wound filaments.

Figure 2. Meridional cross-section of the torus (plane through the torus hole): evolution of scalar distribution $\chi(\theta, z, t)$

The second row of Fig.2 corresponds to the **meridional cross-section** of the scalar distribution. To obtain this representation, a plane passing through the axis of the torus is considered, for example the plane $y = 0$, and the intersection of the colored surface with this plane is analyzed. In parametric coordinates, this is equivalent to examining the distribution $\chi(\theta, z, t)$ or, after mapping to Cartesian coordinates, the field

$\chi(x, z, t)$ within an annular domain. This cross-section clearly shows how the initially localized scalar patch evolves: first forming an elongated arc, then a thin layer, and eventually several nearly concentric narrow bands. The key significance of this representation is that it provides not only the distribution on the surface, but also its projection onto a more familiar two-dimensional plane, where the process of filamentation is more readily observed.

Figure 3. Unwrapped torus (rectangular coordinates (s, θ)): evolution of scalar distribution $\chi(s, \theta, t)$

The next row of Figure 3 is constructed in the so-called unwrapped toroidal coordinates. Since the surface of a torus is topologically equivalent to the product of two circles $S^1 \times S^1$, it can be “cut” and mapped onto a rectangle in the (s, θ) coordinates following the approach of Arnold [3]. In this representation, scalar transport becomes particularly transparent. In these coordinates, the initial Gaussian patch appears as a compact spot in the rectangular domain; subsequently, due to the non-uniform velocity \dot{s} , the patch deforms into an inclined band and then into a family of nearly parallel slanted filaments that periodically extend across the boundaries. It is precisely in this representation that the

dominant mechanism – shear - becomes most evident. If the velocity ω_s were constant, the patch would be advected without deformation. However, since $\omega'_s(\theta) \neq 0$, a linear growth of phase differences occurs, accompanied by transverse compression. In the unwrapped coordinates, this can be estimated as follows: if the local longitudinal scale grows as

$$\ell_{\parallel}(t) \sim \ell_0(1 + \omega'_s(\theta)t), \quad (15)$$

then the transverse scale decreases as

$$\ell_{\perp}(t) \sim \ell_0/(1 + \omega'_s(\theta)t), \quad (16)$$

under the condition of area preservation in an incompressible (divergence-free) transport on the surface.

Figure 4. Panels (d) and (e) illustrate the quantitative characteristics of the filamentation process of the passive scalar over time. Panel (d) shows the evolution of the maximum scalar gradient $\max|\nabla\chi|$, normalized by its initial value. It is observed that $\max|\nabla\chi|$ increases monotonically and, when plotted on a logarithmic scale, exhibits an approximately linear dependence on time, which corresponds to an exponential law $\max|\nabla\chi| \propto \exp \sigma t$.

Figure 5. Panels (f) and (g) show one-dimensional profiles of the passive scalar χ and the magnitude of its gradient $|\nabla\chi|$ at a late stage of the evolution. Panel (f) presents the profile along a poloidal circle ($s = \text{const}$), *μοδα κακ να γραφικε (g) shows the profile along a toroidal circle ($\theta=0$). In both cases, the values of χ (blue curve) and $|\nabla\chi|$ (red curve) are normalized, with the gradient plotted on a logarithmic scale.*

For quantitative diagnostics, additional plots of gradient growth and transverse thickness decay were included (Fig. 4). The scalar gradient on the toroidal surface is, in principle, computed as a derivative with respect to the intrinsic coordinates, taking into account the surface metric. However, for visualization purposes, a normalized quantity equivalent to

$$|\nabla\chi| \sim \sqrt{(\partial\chi/\partial s)^2 + (\partial\chi/\partial\theta)^2}. \quad (17)$$

As the *winding* process develops, the scalar filaments become progressively thinner, leading to an increase in $|\nabla\chi|$. This behavior is reflected in the plot as an approximately exponential (or quasi-exponential) growth of the maximum gradient, $\max|\nabla\chi(t)| \sim e^{\sigma t}$, which is consistent with strong stretching and compres-

sion. At the same time, the effective transverse thickness $\sigma_{\perp}(t)$, was evaluated, which in the model decreases as

$$\sigma_{\perp}(t) \sim 1/(1 + \Omega't), \quad (18)$$

that is, in accordance with the kinematic model of differential winding.

Finally (Fig. 5), one-dimensional profiles were computed along a fixed poloidal circle and a fixed toroidal circle. For this purpose, the sections

$$\chi(\theta, t)|_{s=s_0} \text{ and } \chi(s, t)|_{\theta=\theta_0}, \quad (19)$$

were considered, along with the corresponding profiles of $|\nabla\chi|$. At late times, these profiles acquire an oscillatory structure with a large number of narrow peaks. This indicates that the scalar is no longer con-

centrated in a single localized patch, but is instead distributed over a multitude of thin filaments that wrap repeatedly around the torus.

Thus, the construction of the figure 4 involves the following sequence of steps: first, the toroidal geometry is defined in parametric coordinates; next, an initial localized scalar distribution $\chi(s, \theta, 0)$ is prescribed; then, a steady divergence-free velocity field with a non-uniform toroidal component is introduced on the surface; the scalar field is subsequently advected in a Lagrangian manner along trajectories determined by the system for $s(t)$ and $\theta(t)$; the concentration field is then reconstructed and visualized in three forms - on the toroidal surface, in a meridional cross-section, and in the unwrapped (s, θ) ; domain; finally, diagnostic quantities such $\max|\nabla\chi|$, $\sigma_{\perp}(t)$ and one-dimensional profiles are evaluated. The purpose of this visualization is to clearly demonstrate a fundamental mechanism: a localized scalar in a closed three-dimensional flow does not dissipate, but is conserved along trajectories and, under the action of differential advection, is stretched into long, thin filaments that become increasingly tightly wound around the toroidal surface. This provides a geometric picture of advection and filamentation of a passive scalar in three-dimensional space.

5. Discussion. The numerical results demonstrate that, in the absence of diffusion and under a steady velocity field, the dominant mechanism governing the evolution is purely kinematic stretching. As time increases, the initially localized scalar patch is elongated along trajectories, forming thin layers whose thickness decreases while the gradients increase. At later times, the structure becomes multilayered, and the scalar distribution acquires a quasi-periodic character in both the toroidal and poloidal directions. These computational results confirm the theoretical prediction [10, 16] that differential advection along closed trajectories leads to filamentation and the generation of progressively smaller scales even in fully regular three-dimensional flows.

References

1. Aref H. (1984) Stirring by chaotic advection, *J. of Fluid Mech.*, 143, 1-21

2. Aref H. (2002) The development of chaotic advection, *Physics of Fluids*, 14, 1315-1325

3. Arnold V. (1989) *Mathematical Methods of Classical Mechanics*. Springer.

4. Batchelor, G. K. (1967) *An Introduction to Fluid Dynamics*. Cambridge University Press.

5. Balmforth, N. J. (1999) Shear instability and interfacial mixing. *J. of Fluid Mech.*, 387, 97-127.

6. Balmforth N.J. & Young, W.R. (2002) Holmboe waves and layers in stratified shear flow, *J. of Fluid Mech.*, 450, 131-167.

7. Childress St. & Gilbert A.D. (1995) *Stretch, Twist, Fold: The Fast Dynamo*. Springer.

8. Hill M. J. M. (1894) On a spherical vortex. *Phil. Trans. of the Royal Society A*, 185, 213-245.

9. Kozlov V.V., Mamaev, I.S., & Sokolovskiy, M.A. (2007) IUTAM Symposium on Hamiltonian Dynamics, Vortex Structures, Turbulence. IUTAM Bookseries, Vol. 6, Springer.

10. Milyute E. & Milyus A. (2026) Non-destructive Absorption of a Small Counter-rotating Vortex by a Spherical Hill Vortex, *J. The Scientific Heritage*, 183, 71-75

11. Moffatt H.K. & A. Tsinober A. (1992) Helicity in laminar and turbulent flow, *Ann. Review of Fluid Mech.*, 24, 281-312.

12. Moser J. (1973) *Stable and Random Motions in Dynamical Systems*. Princeton University Press.

13. Ottino, J. M. (1989) *The Kinematics of Mixing: Stretching, Chaos, and Transport*. Cambridge University Press.

14. Pierrehumbert, R. T. (1994) Tracer microstructure in the large-eddy dominated regime. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 4, 1091-1110.

15. Thiffeault, J.-L. (2012) Using multiscale norms to quantify mixing and transport. *Nonlinearity*, 25, R1-R44.

16. Rhines P.B. & Young W.R. (1983) How rapidly is a passive scalar mixed within closed streamlines, *J. of Fluid Mech.*, 133, 133-145.

17. Villermaux, E. (2012) Mixing versus stirring. *Annual Review of Fluid Mech.*, 44, 69-90.

18. Young W.R. (1987) Selective decay of enstrophy and the vortical motion of fluids, *J. of Fluid Mech.*, 184, 49-65.